

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Report on the conducted communication and dissemination activities with an update of the communication and dissemination plan.

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WP10

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable updates the nextGEMS project communication and dissemination plan and details activities that have been done in the first half of the project. The main objective of the communication and dissemination activities is to provide regular project communication and dissemination targeting various audiences, from the scientific community to many societal actor groups, as the first step towards a more profound engagement with stakeholders and future users of project results. Besides using standard science communication approaches, such as peer-reviewed articles, participation at conferences, social media and the project website, nextGEMS also explores and applies innovative communication and dissemination approaches and tools. These include Vlogs (the video communication), science explainers and storylines. The communication and dissemination activities are part of WP10 and the Storms & Society theme, and the main two partners responsible for its implementation are Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) and Latest Thinking (LT). However, the activities are deployed in close collaboration with all consortium members and project participants.

2 Conclusion & Results

The project communication and dissemination activities follow the principles of visibility, transparency, plurality and usability. This includes ensuring visibility of the project and its outcomes for a wide range of stakeholder circles; being transparent on the evolution of the nextGEMS scientific production; plurality in the perspectives included and reached with the different communication and dissemination products; and usability by tailoring the scientific outputs with and for different stakeholder groups and using communication approaches for starting knowledge coproduction. Particularly interesting are nextGEMS's three innovative communication and engagement approaches: videos, science explainers and storylines. Developing four different types of videos, nextGEMS tailors them to all six stakeholder groups targeted by the project. So far, the project has produced 17 videos. Already becoming a leitmotif and recognisable mark of nextGEMS, these short, visually appealing, videos prepared in an accessible language are considered extremely powerful communication tools, that can be easily disseminated through social media, showcased at events or distributed in other ways. The next innovative communication tool is science explainers which show the driving ideas and progress from nextGEMS scientists in plain language and different formats. Finally, an important approach for disseminating project outcomes will be through storylines. The co-exploration and co-design activities have already started for the two project storylines, as detailed in [D10.3](#).

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS coproduction, communication & dissemination and video presence (O3)	yes
Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process) (O3)	yes
Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination) (O3)	yes

Objectives of WP10

Relevance in this deliverable?

Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination) (O3)

yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

WP10 provided a communication and dissemination plan (D10.2) at the beginning of the project. The principles that guide the plan are those of visibility, transparency, plurality and usability (Norström et al., 2020). Plurality is being respected by adopting a gender- and diversity-aware approach when engaging with stakeholders, and when designing communication approaches and disseminating information. Along the line the best practices highlighted in the EU project communication guidelines, nextGEMS allocated enough resources to communication and dissemination activities, as key elements of WP10 and the Storms & Society theme. WP10 additionally includes all consortium members, whose collaboration in project communication and dissemination is guided by the project team with expertise on user engagement and communication.

This report details the communication and dissemination activities that took place in the first half of the project.

4.1 nextGEMS audience

nextGEMS defines near-field and far-field stakeholder groups and adjusts different communication and dissemination strategies to each of these groups.

1. The near-field nextGEMS stakeholder groups are formed by the following:

- Scientists: earth science community and wider scientific community;
- Users: users from renewable energy and fisheries;
- Technologists: HPC technologists and high-capacity data experts;

2. The far-field nextGEMS stakeholder groups are formed by the following:

- Policy-makers: policy and decision makers;
- Broader user community: users from other sectors and domains, including climate services and met offices;
- Public and media: general public, including communities from West Africa, and journalists.

Figure 1 shows the communication and dissemination products that each of the stakeholder groups will receive during the project. NextGEMS communication strategy builds on two ideas: tailoring communication and dissemination material to each stakeholder group and putting the emphasis on what is communicated as well as on the process of creating the message. These two ideas, the communication content and process, work together synergistically, allowing us to reach more effectively the audience and increase the awareness about the results of the project, but also a robust legacy with the uptake of its outputs by different communities. This is also aligned with the coproduction paradigm we embraced in nextGEMS (see [D10.1](#) and [D10.3](#)).

Figure 1: NextGEMS stakeholder groups and means and mediums of communication

4.2 Key communication activities

nextGEMS applies standard communication approaches by using the project website, social media, research articles and word of mouth at various conferences and events. In addition, it applies three innovative communication formats: Vlog, science explainers, and storylines. These different product types can more effectively reach different audiences.

4.2.1 Science Explainers

Science explainers present the driving ideas and progress from nextGEMS scientists in plain language. Science Explainers are concise, accessible content designed to make complex scientific concepts understandable to diverse audiences. By implementing a multi-faceted strategy with written formats, video storytelling, and visual design, these explainers serve to enhance transparency, foster public understanding, and may eventually support evidence-based decision-making. The explainers aim to show how scientists think and their way of working and cover a wide range of topics relevant to any audience interested in the latest breakthroughs related to SR-ESMs. This approach gives access to information and explanations that are often not otherwise available to the public. The development of Science Explainers for the nextGEMS project follows a systematic and co-creative approach designed to ensure clarity, accessibility, and scientific accuracy. This process involves close collaboration between scientists, co-production and communication experts, and graphic designers to produce high-impact explainers that address the needs of various stakeholder groups. WP10 developed a template and guidance for preparing science explainers. This guidance provided the key questions for the scientists to focus on while preparing the explainers (See Figure 2):

- Definition: Can you please give us a definition of your topic?

- Research Focus: Is there a hypothesis or expectation driving your research?
- Scientific Debate: How much agreement or disagreement is there in the literature on these points?
- Challenges and Opportunities: What challenges do you face in your research? And what opportunities do you see?
- Interdisciplinarity: What (sub)disciplines and expertise are needed for this research?
- Impact on Stakeholders: What are the expected contributions for: (i) The scientific community? (ii) Policy-making? (iii) Other societal actors?
- Potential for Climate Services: Could this research support adaptation, mitigation strategies, or disaster risk management? If yes, who would be the potential users?

The science explainers which initially were provided as text, have been also complemented with a series of videos, leveraging the power of visual storytelling to engage and inform diverse audiences. Through collaboration between project scientists and Storms & Society theme, the project has so far published the following explainers (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/science-explainers/>):

- Tracking fast-forming and dissipation clouds
- Knowledge networks in NextGEMS
- Scientific and technical challenges of extending a weather model for climate studies
- Understanding aerosols and clouds with storm-resolving simulations
- Tackling the biases of tropical mixed layer depth in ocean models
- Retuning the ocean vertical mixing scheme for storm-resolving models

4.2.2 Storylines

To provide a unity to different components of physical and social aspects of the researched phenomena, the project uses storylines. nextGEMS kick-started the work on the project storylines with the first exploratory storyline workshop that WP10 hosted at the Cycle 2 hackathon in Vienna. This workshop gave preliminary insights into the elements of the storyline development that should be considered.

The work on the energy storyline has started by investigating the narratives in the new Spanish law on Climate change and energy transition and interviewing key national stakeholders. This was further elaborated in a dedicated workshop on co-creating participatory scenarios, that took place during the Cycle 3 hackathon in Madrid in May 2023 (see [D10.3](#)).

Prior to the Workshop, the Science & Society team developed the communication material (in Spanish) to raise awareness, share information, motivate and inspire stakeholders to take part in the workshop. Figure 3 gives a glimpse of this material shared with 50 energy sector stakeholders in Spain.

Figure 2: Guidelines for writing a Science explainer

The Cycle 3 hackathon in Madrid also hosted the first fishery storyline co-design activities. The aim of the storyline is to use nextGEMS data outputs for the scenario storylines (renewable energy) and physical climate storylines (fisheries) (Baulenas et al., 2023). The theoretical bases for the storyline development is provided in a recent nextGEMS publication:

E. Baulenas et al. (2023). “Assembling the climate story: use of storyline approaches in climate-related science”. In: *Global Challenges* 7.7, p. 2200183. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.202200183>

This paper was presented as a poster during EGU2023 (23–28th April 2023) in the session, “Storyline-based climate attribution, projection, process understanding, and impacts”.

4.2.3 Next generation Video Communication Concept

The project has so far produced examples of three (out of four) different types of videos, overall labelled as ‘Vlogs’, a powerful tool for science communication. The videos make it possible for specialists to follow the progress of the project, and at the same time to reach out to and communicate the project idea to broader audience such as policy and decision makers and the general public. nextGEMS videos have been professionally produced by LT. However, after the recent training aimed at enhancing partners’ video recording skills, we expect to have more

crowd sourced videos, prepared by nextGEMS scientists.

These are the videos produced in the first half of the project:

nextGEMS Clips: this is a short-format video, which gives an overview of the project with the use of animations:

1. introductory video "nextGEMS in a Nutshell" ([Video](#))
2. A new approach on climate modelling – Bjorn Stevens ([Video](#))
3. Promising times for the climate application sector – Irina Sandu ([Video](#))
4. Project implementation – Heike Konow and Daniel Klocke ([Video](#))
5. Storms & Radiation – Frida Bender ([Video](#))
6. Storms & Land – Cathy Hohenegger ([Video](#))
7. Storms & Ocean – Noel Keenlyside ([Video](#))
8. Storms & Society – Dragana Bojović ([Video](#))

Research Videos: these videos will be departing from the outputs of nextGEMS research lines, specifically, the aim is to create an animated version of the published articles under the project. This is a communication strategy which has been increasingly applied in recent years, aiming at reaching a broader audience inside and outside the borders of the scientific community.

Progress Videos: this type of videos shows the progress of the project. Especially, it shows the working process of nextGEMS. It can imply, for instance, the 'behind the scenes' of Hackathons or the other activities planned in the deployment of knowledge co-production activities. So far the following progress videos have been recorded:

1. Knowledge networks in nextGEMS ([Video](#))
2. Challenges in model development ([Video](#))
3. Tracking fast-forming and dissipating clouds ([Video](#))
4. Cycle 1 hackathon ([Video](#))
5. Cycle 2 hackathon ([Video](#))
6. Special: Talkround with Masaki Satoh and Bjorn Stevens ([Video](#))
7. Special: The need of effective science communication – Tido Semmler ([Video](#))

A few more interviews were recorded at the Cycle 3 hackathon which are currently under preparation.

Results Videos: this type of video shows the on-going research in layman terms, and it is meant to reach far-field stakeholders interested in the advancement of climate science. The preparation of the results video has started and is planned to continue over the third project year.

4.2.4 Other Communication Approaches

Project partners are encouraged to express their creativity and communicate their work to broader audience via video, text, or a piece of art in a form of figure or climate visualisation.

Standard communication channels: For critical information dissemination, nextGEMS applies standard communication channels, such as website, social media, and visual identity elements, like graphic charter, flyers, and roll ups. Additionally, partners' networks and associated distribution channels also serve to disseminate the outputs produced in nextGEMS. Finally, nextGEMS also uses press releases for further dissemination of the results, as well as participation in different events and clustering with other activities.

Internal communication and office hour: Internally, nextGEMS project partners benefit from communication through mailing list and platforms such as Mattermost, which allows for opening several chats by selected topics. An important arena for regular internal communication and for maintaining strong collaborative relationships is the weekly office hour. The office hour is coordinated by early career scientists (ECS), who select a different project related topic and speaker each week. This helps keep the contact between scientists, in particular ECS, as well as to follow the latest developments in the project in a participatory and fun way.

Blogposts: Project partners are encouraged to publish blogposts, such as the two published on the website:

- Fixing the water and energy budget imbalances in ECMWF's IFS ([link](#))
- Updated nextGEMS models for the next simulation cycle ([link](#))

Visual communication and nextCalendarArt: Visual communication is another strong communication element of nextGEMS. Numerous climate visualisation videos, presenting outputs from nextGEMS models in an attractive way, have been published at the website and on social media.

Art is an important and increasingly used form of scientific expression. To boost the artistic spirit, nextGEMS organises a competition of science-based visualisation pieces each year. The best figures make it into the calendar 'nextCalendarArt'. The calendars for 2022 and 2023 were distributed to the nextGEMS consortium and friends.

Policy briefs: To inform policy makers and the European Commission, nextGEMS will provide policy briefs in the second half of the project. Some topics have already been discussed, such as 'Building User Communities around Next Generation Earth System Models' or 'Food Security in West Africa'.

Meetings, workshops and side events at conferences: The key platform for collaboration in the framework of nextGEMS are hackathons (see [D10.3](#) for more updates), but nextGEMS consortium members also actively participate in other events, including scientific conferences (such as EGU and AGU general assemblies), expert events (e.g. [Berlin Summit for EVE](#)) or

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other events. Figure 2 is an example of the nextGEMS poster presented at the WWRP/SERA "Weather and Society" online conference in 2022.

5 References (Bibliography)

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 Ensuring the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The science explainers are presented in different formats (e.g., blog post, brochure and nextGEMS progress videos. This diversity of formats helps reach different stakeholder com-

munities from the nextGEMS far-field, such as broader user community, public, media, or policymakers. Although the target audience for this type of message are mainly far-field nextGEMS stakeholder groups, it also can provide near-field groups with updates on the progress in the project.

Storylines can be presented in various formats, e.g., web-explorable story-maps, combining text, images and maps with geo-referenced data and simulation output. This type of material is especially adequate for near-field stakeholder groups, the target audience of the nextGEMS storylines, as it involves users additionally in its co-development process. However, we will also use summary reports and progress videos to communicate the key storyline findings to media, broader audience and policymakers. In particular, the fishery storyline that will apply nextGEMS data to better understand marine ecosystem dynamics and changes in the Atlantic Ocean off the west coast of Africa will also target stakeholders and policymakers from this part of the world. The event where the storyline will be presented to gain most visibility is still under discussion.

Videos are an easily accessible communication format both for experts and for broader audience. With 17 published videos and many more in the pipeline, nextGEMS makes sure to maintain high project visibility and effective communication to all its target stakeholder groups. In addition, project scientists received a training to produce videos, which should further enhance this effective communication approach.

nextGEMS simulations are fascinating demonstrations of the latest scientific achievements. Their visual appeal, together with the Vlog's video outputs, makes it very unlikely that the project won't capture the public imagination. Additionally, we share the video outputs across several platforms and conduct social media campaigns, while the consortia members share the videos in their networks.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

There is a link with D10.1, D10.2 and D10.4. The basis for effective Communication and dissemination activities are strong links and communication with the whole project.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19 – 22 October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- WWRP/SERA "Weather and Society" Conference 28 February – 11 March, 2022, online
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01 – 03 April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26 June – 02 July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31 June – 06 July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04 – 06 April 2023
- Storylines presentation, EGU, 23 – 28 April, Vienna, Austria
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29 May – 02 June 2023 in Madrid, Spain

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>

Figure 3: Energy Storyline communication material

The NextGEMS project

NextGEMS builds the next generation of Storm-resolving Earth-system models.

NextGEMS's km scale granularity models will provide a more reliable basis for how the climate will change over the next decades seamlessly at global and regional scales.

NextSociety

Targeting the scales on which impacts of severe weather events are felt, the project brings the science closer to society by:

- 1 Engaging society through Videos and science explainers
- 2 Involving stakeholders at events and through storylines
- 3 Co-developing knowledge at Hackathons

NextGEMS Coproduction

Assessing how hackathons perform in:

- 1 Enabling coproduction
- 2 Bringing, bridging & integrating knowledge
- 3 Accelerating research outcomes
- 4 Enhancing interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity

Storms and Society

Dragana Bojović & Eulàlia Baulenas

Four Project Themes

Radiation

Ocean

Land

Society

NextVideo Concept

VIDEO TYPES

- NextGEMS Clip** ...give an oriented overview of the project in less than 2 minutes
- Research Videos** ...survey content of published journals to a wider audience
- Results Video** ...shows technical information as accessible, respectful and accurate
- Progress Videos** ...give insights about the current status of the project, produced by all teams involved

Coproduction Framework

COPRODUCTION FRAMEWORK for Climate Services

The framework is a circular process involving **SOCIETY** and **STAKEHOLDERS**. The cycle includes: **AWARENESS RAISING**, **ENGAGEMENT**, **KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE**, and **EMPOWERMENT**. Key activities include: Social Media, Websites, NextGEMS VLOGs, Science Explainers, Mailing list, Webinars, gather town, Meetings, Conferences, Workshops, Case studies, and Storylines.

NextGEMS USERS

<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/> @nextgems_eu

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Figure 4: Storms and society poster presentation at the WWRP/SERA "Weather and Society" Conference 2022